

Effects of Retaining Skillful Employees on the Career Management: A Field Study

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Abstract—Enterprises need a strategic plan to retain their skillful employees and provide their career management, sustain their existence, to have growth and leadership qualities, to reach the objectives to increase the value of the enterprise and to not to be affected from changing demographic structure. In the cases when the long term career expectations of skillful employees are in integrity with the enterprise's interests, skill management process is directly related to the career management. With a long term plan, the enterprises should cover the labor force need that may arise in the future by using systematic career development programs and be prepared against developments for all times. Skill management is considered as a practice with which career mobility is planned for the skillful employee to be prepared for high level positions. Career planning is the planning of an employee's progress or promotion within an organization for which he works by developing his knowledge, skills, abilities and motives. Career planning is considered as an individual's planning his future and the position which he wants to have, the area which he want to work in, the objectives which he want to reach. With the aim of contributing the abovementioned discussion process, career management concept and its perception manner are examined in this study in a comparative manner.

Keywords—Skill management, career management, skill, back up, human resources management.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the recent years, enterprises need a strategic plan to retain their skillful employees and provide their career management, sustain their existence, to have growth and leadership qualities, to reach the objectives to increase the value of the enterprise and to not to be affected from changing demographic structure.

Career is to progress in a selected job progress and to earn more money, to undertake more responsibilities and to obtain more power and reputation as a result of this. It is the whole attitude and behaviors which a person perceived regarding experiences and activities about the job he has acquired during his lifetime.

Career planning is the planning of an employee's progress or promotion within an organization for which he works by developing his knowledge, skills, abilities and motives. Career planning is considered as an individual's planning his future and the position which he wants to have, the area which he

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want to work in, the objectives which he want to reach.

Career plans puts forward the cornerstones for this purpose. If these cornerstones have been placed consciously and an access has been provided the individual's feeling for reaching the success will be more strengthened. Thus, these feeling will make individual satisfaction and motivation to increase.

Career development stage is considered both as the process of switching among organizations and from one job to another. The interest of the person slides from the security need to the need of success, reputation and independency. Needs of people goes up according to the needs hierarchy of Maslow. Predominantly the desires to switch to jobs which require leadership and responsibility qualities are observed with the employees [1].

Career development is accepted as the conscious activities which contribute to career selection and the sufficiency and self-respect satisfaction of the employee by adapting healthy to this career selection.

On the other hand, an individual development catalogue may be given for contributing the personal developments of the skillful employees. Individual development catalogue, which includes the resources that the employees can use regarding the sufficiency's they need to develop, are considered as useful applications for skillful employees who undertake personal responsibility and also for the other employees [2].

II. INCREASING THE EFFORT TO RETAIN SKILLFUL EMPLOYEES

Hiring, training, motivation and long term employment of the skillful employees are considered as the most important function of human resources with the changes occurring in the markets affected by the globalization it is getting harder to retain skillful employees.

The most important principles and suggestions regarding the issue of increasing the efforts for retaining skillful employees are ordered below and these suggestions will be effective in career managements of the skillful employees [3].

- Activity should be started by stating that the expectations of the parties in this psychological contract, which is the unwritten contract between the employee and the enterprise, changed.
- Attracting skillful employees to the enterprise and retaining them should be a priority for the senior management.
- Policies and applications, which will increase the attractiveness of the enterprise for employees, should be applied and conducted.

- Needs of unit managers which are skillful and responsible should be covered.
- Value must be added to the positions that the employees qualified for.
- Learning and personal development opportunities regarding career plans should be provided to the employees.
- Personal efforts of the employees should be supported and a flow of information regarding the subject should be provided.
- Facts regarding the job should be notified to the employee.
- Roles of human resources managers should be rearranged.
- The enterprise should establish its own talent pool.

Various applications are observed in the enterprise in Turkey in terms of increasing

The efforts for retaining the skillful employees. If we are to sort some of them [4]:

Borusan Holding provides seminars, courses and web-based training regarding the personal development of its employees. Rotation application is being done for the employees among affiliated enterprises and the positions in such enterprises. Employees who have high performances are raised as executive candidates by career planning programs. Success of the employee is rewarded with performance-based fee and incentive bonuses.

Anadolu Group tries to develop their human resources systems further by examining the results of the strategies developed for attracting skillful employees to their own group and retaining them. It is aimed to make the qualities of the employees compatible with the positions they are in. Also, investment is made on employees' developing their qualities. For this purposes, a job environment, which support developing themselves and their jobs, is created.

Arçelik has been preparing a development plan to not to lose skillful candidates. Trainings are organized for the employees' developments and relevant support is provided. Planning of enterprise career is made accordingly.

III. CAREER REVITALIZING STRATEGY INTENDED FOR SKILLFUL EMPLOYEES

Technological changes occurring in recent years, globalization movements causing changes in structures of the enterprises and the change process occurring in the qualities of personnel which is required have caused for the employees to go back in higher career, that is to say enter the career plateau [5].

By means of providing career vitalization education for the employees in career plateau, it will be possible for employees, who were previously considered as skillful and who found themselves in career plateau with the effects of globalization, to survive in this situation.

It will be useful for the institutions to take some steps which are considered important for revitalizing their employees with careers. The relevant works should be started with removing the obstacles before occupational mobility. After that, it will be necessary to determine skillful employees

by using performance management system of the enterprise. It will be useful to apply some basic tools regarding such employees [6].

- Assigning new tasks to the skillful employees,
- Providing career change within the enterprise,
- Giving management, education and information share responsibility to skillful employees,
- Organizing refreshing educations,
- Providing long term vacations with pay,
- Organizing leadership development programs.

Vitalizing the career of skillful employees this way, it will be provided for the career to be replanned and the plans made regarding his career to be realized [7].

IV. CAREER CHANGES OF SKILLFUL EMPLOYEES

It is possible to attribute career changing reasons of skillful employees to three basic principles. *Occupational dissatisfaction* resulting from the fact that the employee works in an occupational area which is not suitable for his qualities, interest and personality structure is considered as the first reason.

We see the second reason as change in the values loaded to the occupational areas by the society. This situation changes by the time. Even if he/she is happy, the individual thinks of switching to another job which will provide him/her more income and social facilities.

The third reason is that some occupational areas may be affected by the crisis environments more deeply. For this reason, the employees want to find jobs which are not so open to crisis.

V. METHODS OF SKILLFUL EMPLOYEES TO SURVIVE FROM MID-CAREER CRISES

All the situations like the possibilities to advance in the job getting reduced, decrease of efficiency and leaving the organization, change in transfer and promotion measures, competition and fear of death in middle aged employees brings on a situation known as *middle age crisis* [1].

The most important reasons for the employees in the working environment are that they think they lack some skills, they cannot adapt to technological developments and they feel exhausted. Motivating employees in such situations is quite difficult.

The point which employees encounter during the mid-life of their careers or which important advances and development for their careers stop is defined as career plateau or career flattening.

The solution to this problem which the employees encounter during the mid-life of their jobs will only be provided by conducting an efficient career consultancy service and the support that the executive staff may provide these employees during this time. The management may delay the employee's entrance time to career plateau or exterminate this situation completely [8] by means of precautions it will take and educational activities it will organize.

It will be useful for the enterprise to make some evaluations in order to understand whether the employees, who are in the

middle of their career lives, are available for vitalizing their careers and to be encouraged.

1. In addition to the employees who are on their way to leadership, who are the employees having skills, experience, attitude and adaptation needed most in the long-term?
2. Which employees who are in the middle of their career lives need to revitalize their careers?
3. Is there any method being applied for the employees who are in the middle of their career lives?
4. How free the experience, knowledge and ability wanders within the enterprise? Is it possible for the employees to switch places within the enterprise? What are the elements defecting the institutional operation?
5. With which sustainability is it provided that each task will be done in a way to develop not only the performance of the enterprise but also the individual performance of the employee?
6. Is it possible to provide new tasks to the employees when their social status changes?
7. Is career change of employees within the enterprise encouraged?
8. Are paid leaves with time provided for the employees?
9. Which is prioritized while employing people, the people who are in the middle of their careers or the people who will be employed for the first time?
10. Is it known for the candidates who are in the middle of their career lives that which jobs will be more suitable for them?

The enterprises need to prepare support programs for providing the employees with opportunities to survive mid-career crises. Also, it should be stated to the skillful employees that they may use their experiences during the mid-career time [9]. Especially special effort is needed for employing the skillful personnel [1].

VI. BACK-UPS PROGRAMS FOR SKILLFUL EMPLOYEES

The real purpose of the work force planning made by the human resources departments is to predict the staff that will be needed in the future and to make them join the structure of the enterprise.

Enterprises which give importance to develop higher role models especially for the employees working in critical positions use back-up and talent pool establishing systems. Employees suitable for the vacant positions to occur and who are also conformist people will be reached in the fastest manner with the backup and talent pool system to be established.

The enterprises need to have backup plans ready in their hands to employ people without losing time instead of the ones who have been working in critical positions but who have left their jobs by their own will or who are laid off from their jobs by the decision of managers or the enterprise owner [10].

Backup planning is the process during which the enterprise determines people for critical leadership levels who are skillful and who have suitable career background and

potential for the relevant positions before a period of time which is critical for the organization and to develop the leadership developments of these people thus making them ready to the position in question [11].

After the backup plans are decided by the managers the backup phase will start. The major stages of this phase are as follows [12]:

- Determination of backup need,
- Determination of employee profile,
- Determination of needs for advance,
- Determination of advance activities,
- Implementation of advance activities.

An effective backup planning requires determination and preparation of right skillful people for the right positions at the right time. At this stage performance evolution methods can be used [13]. On the other hand, it is taken into consideration which will be the qualities that are expected from the employees.

Executive of the enterprises in Turkey focus on the performances of the employee regarding his/her job, his experiences, his time of work within the institution and his compatibility rather than questioning his qualification and levels for this job. The examinations that are made have revealed that many employees who had high performance in their specializations could not display managerial qualities at the same level [14].

VII. IMPORTANCE OF RESEARCH

A. Environment of the Study and Sample Selection

Environment of the study is constituted of 4 and 5 star hotels acting in Ankara. The reason why 4 or 5 star hotels in the sector is selected is that the number of skillful employees with qualities they employed is high and they have long term process which requires investments in career management activities. According to the data obtained from the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, support is requested from all hotels with 4 or 5 stars (29 four star hotels – 11 five star hotels) acting in Ankara to participate in survey study. However, some hotel enterprises could not participate in survey studies because of the density of their business.

B. Preparation of Application of the Survey

Data have been collected by means of surveys in the study. The survey is constituted of two parts. Personal information has taken place in the first part (gender, age, employment time in the enterprise, marital status, the department of employment) whereas career questions have taken place in the second place. The survey applied in the study has been used by Puah and Anantham (2006) and Kırçcı has used this survey (2007) in his study by translating it into Turkish. There are 19 questions in the scale that has been used under with the topics of career planning, career management and career development. First 9 questions in the survey is about career planning whereas the next 6 questions are about career management and last 4 questions are about career development. 5 questions regarding career management of the skillful employees working in the enterprise have been added

to these questions and the survey has been prepared as 5 point likert scale.

Human resources managers of the hotels have been contacted and the surveys have been filled by the hotel employees with rest breaks. 300 surveys have been sent to the hotel enterprises in question. 168 of these surveys have been returned and 154 surveys have been taken into consideration.

The survey used in the study as data collection tool has been subjected to reliability analysis and Cronbach has been determined as Alpha = 0.91. At the lower levels career planning dimension has been determined as $\alpha=0.86$ whereas career management dimension is determined as $\alpha=0.78$, career development dimension as $\alpha=0.61$ and career management of skillful employees as $\alpha=0.67$. According to the results Cronbach Alpha values of the general scale and its lower dimensions are at a pretty reliable and acceptable level in terms of social sciences. business.

C. Data Analysis

A database is established on computer environment after the answers given to the calculation tools by the participants of the survey have been returned and SPSS 11.0 (Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences) statistics package program has been used in the evaluation of the results.

Firstly frequency percentage management methods for demographic information have been used in solving the data obtained as a result of the survey. Frequency-percentage, arithmetic mean and standard deviation values of the questions in the second part of the survey have been examined.

“t test” and “Anova test”, which are parametric tests, have been used to check whether or not there is a difference between individual properties of the participants and the lower dimensions at the significance level of 0.05. the relation between the sub-dimensions of the survey regarding career management has been analyzed with “Pearson Correlation” method.

D. Findings and Interpretation

Definitive statics regarding the demographic qualities of the people who participated in the study, frequency-percentage distribution of the answers given to the career management scales, arithmetic mean values and standard deviation values have been given in this section. T test and Anova test have been used to analyze whether or not there is a significant difference between career management and demographic properties of the employees and the relation between the relations between the sub-dimensions of the career management survey has been analyzed with Pearson Correlation method. Relevant findings and comments have been added for these analyses. Whether there is a significant difference between the sub-dimension of the career perception or not has been studied with a correlation analysis at the significance level of 0.05. Pearson correlation coefficient between the career plan and career management has been determined as $r=0.747$ and $p=0.000$ in the table.

TABLE I
PEARSON CORRELATION TABLE OF THE CAREER PERCEPTION OF THE EMPLOYEES PARTICIPATING IN THE STUDY BY SUB-DIMENSIONS

	Pearson Correlation (r)	Career Plan	Career Management	Career Development	Career Management of Skillful Employees
Career Plan	R	-	0.747	0.681	0.600
	P	.000	.000	.000	.000
Career Management	R	0.747	-	0.589	0.568
	P	.000	.000	.000	.000
Career Development	R	0.681	0.589	-	0.622
	P	.000	.000	.000	.000
Career Management of Skillful Employees	R	0.600	0.568	0.622	-
	P	.000	.000	.000	.000

According to this relation between the career management and career plan to the positive directional high power (correlation). $r=0.600$ and $p=0.000$ have been determined between career plan and career development. According to this, there is a middle level relation on positive direction between career management and career development. Pearson correlation coefficient between career management and career development has been determined as $r=0.747$ and $p=0.000$. There is a middle level relation on the positive direction between career management and career development. $r=0.568$ and $p=0.000$ have been determined between career management and career management of the skillful employees and it has been determined that there is a middle level relation on the positive direction between career management and the career management of the skillful employees. Pearson correlation coefficient between career development and career management of the skillful employees has been determined as $r=0.622$ and $p=0.000$. According to this, it has been determined that there is a middle level relation on the positive direction between career development and the career development of the skillful employees.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The most important problem that the enterprises which want to create difference and survive in the dense completion environment in international and national areas is having skillful employees and retaining them. In the working environment of the present day, where we don't have few numbers of skillful employees, it has become one of the prioritized subjects for the human resources departments to reach these skillful employees, to attract them to the enterprise, to retain them and to display an attitude suitable for their career expectations.

The studies that have been conducted have shown that the whole enterprise should adopt the career management understanding of the skillful employees. It is deemed important in terms of reaching the result that top management needs to accept and implement the skill management and this should be accepted by all levels of the management.

Another issue which will be paid attention in career management is that the understanding regarding the skillful employees is compatible with the general strategy of the enterprise. It is impossible for an application which is not compatible with the general strategy to be successful. For this

reason, with the aim of supporting the career management of the skilful employees, a talent pool needs to be prepared by using various resources for current staff and the positions to occur [2].

If the fact that the skillful employees are the one who will create a difference in the enterprises is taken into consideration and the career of the values that are owned are managed in a good manner, competitive superiority and success will be obtained and the investment made regarding this issue will be the most accurate and most profitable investment.

According to findings obtained from the study it has been determined that there is a significant difference between skillful employees' career management, its subdivisions and age. It is possible to say that young employees are more conscious regarding careers by considering the mean values. It has been seen that people who worked in hotel enterprises for less time have had higher expectations regarding careers. It has been determined that career expectation of the married people are higher when compared to single people and career expectations increased as the education level of the employees increased. It has been revealed that there is a significant difference between the department of employment and the sub dimensions of career perception such as career planning, career management, career development and career management of the skillful employees. When the hotel enterprises are taken into consideration by the number of star it can be said that the mean values of 5 star hotels are higher. So, it can also be said that career expectations of the employees working in 5 star hotels are higher. Thus, it is possible to mention a significant relation between career development and career advance of the skillful employees.

At the end of the study that has been conducted it is seen that career management of the skillful employees is also important for the efficiency and activity of the enterprise. The study also reveals the effect of retaining skilful employees on career management. Within this context, the enterprise managers should lead the career development of the employees and provide them with the necessary support.

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